

CURRENT STATE OF TRAINING QUALIFIED SPECIALISTS FOR INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES AND FURTHER INCREASING THE INTELLECTUAL AND PROFESSIONAL POTENTIAL OF PERSONNEL IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the current state of training qualified specialists for the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan and increasing the intellectual and professional potential of personnel. It analyzes the modern system of training employees of internal affairs bodies, the legal and regulatory framework of the educational and professional development process, as well as practical measures being implemented within the framework of reforms. The article examines the use of innovative technologies, foreign experience, and modern educational methods in the development of the intellectual potential of personnel. In addition, existing problems and their solutions, as well as proposals for further improving the effectiveness of personnel training, are presented.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, training of specialists, intellectual potential, professional qualifications, personnel policy, education system, reforms, innovative technologies, legal framework, Republic of Uzbekistan, effectiveness.

Ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms in the social life of our country, further socio-economic development of the country, and the establishment of stability, peace, and tranquility, in particular, improving the well-being of the population, is an important condition for achieving the goals of the large-scale reforms being carried out to build a legal democratic state.

It can be said that today a unique, integrated legal system has been created in our country for the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the protection of public order, ensuring the security of the individual, society, and the state, and the prevention of offenses.

In particular, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies from the first days of our country's independence to the present day. Significant work has been done, in particular, on the development and strengthening of the lower level of internal affairs bodies, organized to maintain public order in mahallas, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime. This made it possible to increase the effectiveness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, ensure a peaceful and tranquil life for citizens, and prevent crime in our country.

At the same time, it is no exaggeration to say that the emerging challenges and threats in the world today, namely, international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, and the increasing spread of alien ideas among young people, pose new tasks for internal affairs bodies to prevent and eliminate them in a timely manner. In other words, the consistent continuation of the aforementioned reforms in order to more effectively ensure peace and tranquility, public order, and public safety in our country is a requirement of the times.

In particular, in order to ensure public safety in the country, form an integrated system for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, establish the effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the republican level and strengthen law and order, ensure peace and tranquility of the population by introducing modern working methods, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level"[1] was adopted. In particular, this Decree defines the following as fundamentally new mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies:

- solving problems related to crime prevention and combating crime directly on the ground by identifying and eliminating the causes of crime in the context of each mahalla, family, and individual;
- categorization of each district, city, and mahalla, based on the state of crime in the regions, and involvement of all necessary forces and means to eliminate "hotbeds of crime" in cooperation with khokimiyats, sectors, and the public;
- ensuring peace and stability in our country through the introduction of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms based on the "republic - region - district - mahalla" system, effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs bodies and other state bodies to ensure public safety;
- creating a modern image of internal affairs officers, increasing their responsibility and professional potential, forming the necessary skills to combat new forms of crime, and achieving full digitalization of the sphere.

In addition, in accordance with this Decree, in order to further enhance the role and responsibility of internal affairs bodies in ensuring the effective implementation of new mechanisms for ensuring public safety, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 No. PP-5050 "On Additional Organizational Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Sphere of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime"[2] was adopted, and this resolution approved the "Concept for Organizing Spiritual and Educational Work in Internal Affairs Bodies," and also determined the organization of work to enhance the spiritual and intellectual potential of internal affairs officers based on the conceptual idea "Loyal service to the Motherland and the people is our highest duty!". In particular, one of the main tasks in this regard is the training of mature, qualified specialists for the system of internal affairs bodies, and the further enhancement of the intellectual and professional potential of personnel.

It should be noted that the training of qualified personnel is a requirement of the times. Especially in the current conditions of globalization and a market economy, the issue of training highly qualified, knowledgeable, responsible, and competitive personnel has become more relevant than ever. It is no secret that highly qualified personnel play an important role in the economic, political, and socio-economic development of any state.

In particular, today in our country, in order to train specialists for internal affairs bodies and further enhance their intellectual and professional potential, special attention is paid to targeted professional training of personnel, thorough training in specialties and legal disciplines, combat and physical training. In particular, to achieve these goals, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring

Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 15, 2021 No. PP-5076 "On Measures to Introduce a Qualitatively New System for Training Professional Personnel for Internal Affairs Bodies" was adopted.

In accordance with this resolution, in order to introduce a completely new system for training specialists for internal affairs bodies, ensure career growth of employees based on their qualifications, as well as further enhance the intellectual and professional potential of managerial personnel in the effective management of forces and resources:

- Starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, a two-stage higher education system, including bachelor's and master's degrees, has been introduced into the personnel training process at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the task has been set to qualitatively implement a two-stage higher education system, organize the educational process based on the most modern pedagogical and information technologies, and enhance the scientific and pedagogical potential of the teaching staff, including through their training in foreign educational institutions.

Also, by this resolution, the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs was granted the status of a legal entity, and the following were defined as the main areas of its activity:

special professional training of sergeant personnel in the field of organizing activities to ensure public safety in all areas of sectoral services of internal affairs bodies;

training of employees appointed for the first time to positions of rank-and-file and officer corps of internal affairs bodies based on training programs for initial professional training;

organization of retraining and advanced training of all categories of employees of internal affairs bodies using innovative information and pedagogical technologies, including on the basis of republican higher educational institutions of related fields.

Implementation of the practice of conducting distance and mobile field courses to ensure the advanced training of internal affairs officers directly on-site without interruption from service.

The introduction of a system of continuous educational and career processes into the procedure for service in the internal affairs bodies from September 1, 2021, and the mandatory study of the Academy's master's programs in the specialties "Organizational-Tactical Management" and "Organizational-Strategic Management" for appointment to the relevant positions of the leading personnel of the internal affairs bodies, as well as the requirement for employees to undergo retraining and advanced training courses as one of the main requirements for assigning special ranks and appointing employees of rank and file and sergeant ranks to officer positions, as well as the introduction in 2021 The rules stipulating that from September 1, only persons with higher education will be admitted to serve in sergeant positions of internal affairs bodies, and candidates for rank-and-file positions of internal affairs bodies will be admitted only from among graduates of departmental academic lyceums, military-academic lyceums, assistants to prevention inspectors, as well as persons with higher education or studying in correspondence form of education, were specifically noted.

In pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level," another

resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 15, 2021 No. PP-5077 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Training Professional Personnel in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety" [4] was adopted, in accordance with which the Military-Technical Institute of the National Guard was transformed into the University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the university was designated as a basic higher military educational and research institution carrying out targeted training of qualified personnel for the following areas:

- for the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Guard - in the areas of ensuring public safety, respectively, the protection of public order, road safety, and the implementation of the requirements of the passport system;
- For the Armed Forces and other law enforcement agencies - in the field of military diplomacy, jurisprudence and economics, as well as engineering-technical, educational-psychological and command-tactical activities;
- for state and economic management bodies that have their own security structures - in all areas of organization and implementation of security activities.

In conclusion, the purpose of the above-mentioned regulatory legal acts, adopted on the basis of the promising reforms being implemented in our country, is to improve the system of training highly qualified specialists in the field of preventing any threats to the peace and tranquility of our country and combating crime based on advanced international standards, as well as to increase the personnel potential of law enforcement agencies, in particular, internal affairs bodies, based on modern requirements.

It is also advisable to train mature, qualified specialists for the system of internal affairs bodies in maintaining public order and ensuring public safety in our country, to further enhance the intellectual and professional potential of personnel, to systematically organize spiritual and educational work in the system and increase the effectiveness of measures taken in this area, to increase the intellectual potential, thinking and worldview of personnel, to strengthen their ideological immunity, to develop measures for the further development of the spiritual and moral consciousness of personnel who live with a sense of patriotism and service to the interests of the people, as well as to popularize a healthy lifestyle among them.

Literature:

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